

Identification of Slightly Halophilic Bacteria From Salted Sheepskin Samples and Investigation of Their Biotechnological Importance

DILEK YALCIN¹, PINAR CAGLAYAN^{2*} and DIDEM BERBER³

¹ Marmara University, Institute of Pure and Applied Sciences, Ziverbey, 34722, Istanbul, Türkiye

² Marmara University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology, Division of Plant Diseases and Microbiology, Ziverbey, 34722, Istanbul, Türkiye

³ Maltepe University, Fine and Arts Faculty, Gastronomy and Culinary Department, 34857 Istanbul, Türkiye

Summary

In the leather industry, skins/hides are salted immediately after the animal is slaughtered to prevent the enzymatic activities of bacteria. Although the salt-curing method prevents the growth of mesophilic bacteria, halophilic bacteria can develop in skins/hides that are stored for a long time, causing a decrease in leather quality. In the literature, it has been stated that slightly halophilic bacteria are isolated from products with a certain concentration of salt content. Since there is no study on the presence of these bacteria in salted raw hides, slightly halophilic bacteria were isolated and molecularly identified from ten sheepskin samples which were stored at 20°C for 6 months in our study. Also their biotechnologically important enzymes were evaluated, their bacteriocin production capacity was determined and the antibacterial efficacy of a chemical (sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate) used in the leather industry at certain concentrations were tested against these isolates. The total number of slightly halophilic bacteria, the total number of proteolytic slightly halophilic bacteria and the total number of lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria in skin samples were determined as $1 \times 10^4 - 4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g, $2 \times 10^3 - 4 \times 10^4$ CFU/g and $1 \times 10^2 - 3 \times 10^4$ CFU/g, respectively. A total of 20 slightly halophilic bacteria were isolated from skin samples. Gram-positive and rod-shaped isolates showed optimum growth at 3-5% salt, 37°C-45°C and pH7-8. Protease, lipase, DNase, pullulanase, xylanase and cellulase produced by 100%, 61%, 83%, 11%, 44%, 88% isolates, respectively. In addition, oxidase and catalase activities were detected in all isolates. It has been determined that the isolates were able to produce acids from different sugar sources (D-xylose, D-mannose, D-ribose, sucrose) and can use amino acids (L-cysteine, L-glycine, L-alanine, L-threonine) found in the skin's structure. According to the 16S rRNA sequence analysis results, the isolates belonged to the *Bacillus* genus (*B. rugosus*, *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. haynesii*, *B. aerius*, *B. safensis*, *B. pumilus*, *B. kochii*, *B. mojavensis* and *B. atrophaeus*). Among all isolates producing bacteriocin, the bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus aerius* had a thermostable structure, did not lose its activity at high pH and salt values, completely inactivated its activity when treated with proteinase K enzyme, and had its antibacterial activity when treated with lipase enzyme. Therefore, considering that some species are resistant to antimicrobials, purified bacteriocins can be used as a preservative in the leather industry. The isolates were sensitive to tested chemical substance at a certain concentrations (4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.2, 15.6, 7.8 µg/mL) and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) were detected. The MIC values of the isolates were determined as 62.5 µg/mL (*B. rugosus*), 31.2 µg/mL (*B. haynesii*, *B. safensis*, *B. mojavensis*), 15.6 µg/mL (*B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. aerius*, *B. kochii*), 7.8 µg/mL (*B. pumilus*) and 3.9 µg/mL (*B. atrophaeus*). In this way, unnecessary use of chemicals in the soaking process will be prevented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Animal skins/hides present an excellent environment for the development of micro-organisms as they contain high levels of structural protein (0.3% elastin, 2% keratin, 29% collagen), non-structural protein (1% albumin, globulin, 0.7% mucin, mucoids), mineral salts (0.5%), fat (2%) and water (64%).¹ The protection of fresh raw skins/hides includes temporary preservation processes to prevent micro-organisms harmful to the leather from digesting the nutrients in the skin structure. If the fresh raw skins/hides cannot be preserved immediately, the quality of the finished leather is adversely affected and this undesirable situation causes economic losses. The most commonly utilised preservation methods are curing the skin/hide

with dry salt or brine. The salt curing method ensures that the water is removed from skin by penetration into the skin layer of the salt. In this way, the amount of water required for the enzymatic activities of micro-organisms decreases.² Although this salinity is not suitable for the growth of mesophilic micro-organisms, halophilic bacteria can tolerate this excess salt and maintain their vitality despite high salt concentrations.^{3,4} From this point of view, if the salts used for the preservation of the skins/hides are not processed, the halophilic micro-organisms in the salts penetrate the skin and contaminate the leather.^{2,5,6} There are many studies supporting this in the literature. For example, the presence of various halophilic bacteria and archaeal populations in salt samples used for curing the skins/hides was reported

*Corresponding author e-mail: pinar.caglayan@marmara.edu.tr

in a previous study.⁷ In another study, high numbers of halophilic populations in salt samples utilised in preservation of raw hides, and also in salted hide samples.^{8,9} The existence of moderately halophilic bacteria and extremely halophilic archaea has also been reported in salted sheep and goat skins.^{5,10} From these studies, it was concluded that contamination may occur during stacking in raw hide warehouses, environmental conditions are effective on bacterial growth, and the quality of the salt used is also important. Therefore, it is necessary to control halophilic bacterial populations because when irreversible damage occurs on the skin, it is not possible to reverse it in any way in further beamhouse and tanning stages. Halophilic micro-organisms, which can grow in high salinity conditions, are found in salt lakes, salt production facilities, spas, salted fish, salty fermented foods and on the surface of skins.^{3,11-14}

Halophilic micro-organisms are divided into various groups depending on the salt concentrations in which they can grow optimally. Among halophilic micro-organisms, slightly halophilic bacteria show optimum growth at 0.2-0.5M (1-3%) NaCl concentration.¹⁵ The presence of slightly halophilic bacteria was reported from Korea's traditional salted fermented product Jeotgal,¹⁶ in sediment samples,¹⁷ Thai shrimp paste,¹⁸ in salt water samples from the Colombian Andes,¹⁹ from seawater²⁰ and hypersaline wetland samples²¹ were isolated. On the other hand, there is no study in which slightly halophilic bacteria were isolated and molecularly identified from salt-preserved sheepskins. In this context, it is of great importance to identify slightly halophilic bacteria that can be encountered in the leather industry, to examine their enzyme activities, and to determine the damages on the skin that these bacteria can potentially cause. It has been found by researchers that enzymes such as protease and lipase produced by halophilic micro-organisms cause grain damage, deterioration in skin structure, hair loss, and bad odour.^{4,10,14,22} In this respect, it is also important to determine whether slightly halophilic bacterial isolates have protease and lipase activities. On the other hand, it has been reported that hydrolytic enzymes (DNase, lipase, cellulase, protease, xylanase, amylase, pullunase, urease, β -galactosidase) produced by halophilic bacteria have the potential to be used in many areas such as medicine, detergent, cosmetics, food and leather industry. Proteases and lipases are important as they are mainly used in leather washing, degreasing, tanning, soaking and the final stages of leather processing. Investigation of hydrolytic enzymes produced by slightly halophilic bacteria is important for future studies to determine their usability in leather industry.²³⁻²⁵

One of the other issues to be overcome in terms of the leather sector is the resistance of bacteria to the antibacterial agents used. It is reported that micro-organisms develop resistance to antimicrobial substances that are used excessively and unconsciously in the leather industry.^{4,23,26,27} For this reason, it is also important to determine the effectiveness of antimicrobial agents used in the leather

industry on slightly halophilic bacteria. Because when the leather processing stages are considered, it is possible that they can be seen in the next processing steps, for example, in the soaking process, since they can live in lower salinity compared to extremely halophilic micro-organisms. In order to eliminate these organisms, it is necessary to test the effectiveness of the chemicals currently used in the leather industry. For this purpose, the antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of antimicrobial agent containing sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate used in the leather industry on slightly halophilic bacteria species was investigated in our study. Investigating the minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) is important in terms of determining the effectiveness of this antimicrobial agent on bacteria that can damage the skin in the processing steps of leather.²⁷ Furthermore, it is important to investigate different antimicrobial agents that can be used as an alternative approach to commonly utilised antimicrobial agents in leather industry in order to solve antimicrobial resistance increasing problem globally. The fact that micro-organisms have developed resistance to existing antimicrobial agents now reveals the fact that these chemicals will not be able to control bacteria. As one of alternative approaches, we encounter bacteriocins, which many researchers focus on due to being a natural source, and which have low toxicity in the food industry in the fight against food pathogens.²⁸ Bacteriocins, which are low molecular weight proteins or peptides and synthesised in ribosomes, act by antagonistically on bacteria, stopping the growth of bacteria or killing bacteria.^{29,30} In previous studies, the bacteriocin production capacity of various halophilic bacteria isolated from hides, fermented foods and salted fish was investigated.^{26,31,32} For example, in one study the researchers isolated 25 halophilic archaea strains from samples taken from salterns such as Kaldirim and Kayacik.³¹ Lipase producer strains were found at a rate of 39% in the samples taken from the Kaldirim Saltern and 43% in the samples taken from the Kayacik Saltern. In the continuation of the same study, it was reported that 89% of the strains in the samples taken from the Kaldirim Saltern and 29% of the strains in the samples from the Kayacik Saltern produced halosin against each other.³¹ As a result of that study, they suggested that halosin producing strains or their extracts during the brining process in leathers can be used in the leather industry to control lipase producing strains.³¹ However, there are no studies on the bacteriocin production potential of slightly halophilic bacteria. In this context, the potential of slightly halophilic bacteria to produce bacteriocin was investigated in our study. Bacteriocins obtained from slightly halophilic bacteria, which show antimicrobial activity at different salt concentrations, pH values and temperatures, have a high potential to be used in different processing stages of the leather industry.

In this study, it was aimed to determine the colony shape of slightly halophilic bacterial isolates, to examine Gram staining reactions of the isolates, to

determine their ability to use different carbon sources and amino acids, to determine the optimum salt concentrations, pH and temperature values. In addition, it is aimed to determine bacterial strains with hydrolytic activity that can damage the skin, to investigate their bacteriocin production capacity and to determine the concentrations at which an antimicrobial chemical used in the leather industry can inhibit slightly halophilic bacterial strains.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Collection of salted sheepskin samples

The ten salted sheepskin samples which were stored at 20°C for six months, were taken from the tanneries in Tuzla-Istanbul Organised Leather Industry Zone, Turkey. The samples were then brought to the laboratory immediately for analysis in sterile bags containing ice cubes. In our study, all sheepskin samples were coded between SaShS1 to SaShS10.

2.2 Total number of slightly halophilic bacteria and isolation process

To determine the total number of slightly halophilic bacteria in salted sheepskin samples, 10g of each skin sample, was placed in sterile flasks containing 90ml of 3% NaCl sterile saline. The flasks were incubated in a shaking incubator (IKA REO Basic C) for 3 hours at 37°C at 200rpm. The direct and serial dilutions (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}) of the bacterial suspension were spread onto the surface of the agar plates of Complex Medium (234g NaCl, 0.25g NaHCO_3 , 0.7g NaBr, 9g agar, 39g $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.5g yeast extract, 6g KCl, 61g $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1g CaCl_2 , 1000ml sterile distilled water) containing 3% salt. Petri dishes were incubated for twenty-four hours at 37°C. The growing colonies on the agar plates were counted for the determination of total number of slightly halophilic bacteria in salted sheepskin samples. Then, the morphologically different colonies were selected and streaked onto agar plates of Complex Media containing 3% salt. The process was repeated until pure bacterial cultures were obtained.³³

2.3 Detection of total numbers of proteolytic and lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria

The number of slightly halophilic bacteria with proteolytic activity present in salted sheepskins was investigated using Gelatin Agar Medium including 2g glucose, 6g peptone, 18g agar, 6g yeast extract, 1000ml SW3 (234g NaCl, 1g CaCl_2 , 0.7g NaBr, 61g $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 6g KCl, 0.25g NaHCO_3 , 39g $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1000ml distilled water), 10g gelatin. Direct and serial dilutions (10^{-1} - 10^{-6}) of bacterial suspensions spread on Gelatin Agar Medium. Petri dishes were incubated for twenty-four hours at 37°C. Frazier reagent was poured onto petri dishes. Transparent areas formed around bacterial colonies were evaluated as positive activity and positive colonies were counted. The total number of lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria was examined

using Tween 80 Agar including 1000ml SW3, 20g agar, 10g Tween 80, 5g yeast extract. Direct and serial dilutions (10^{-1} - 10^{-6}) of bacterial suspensions spread on Tween 80 Agar. Petri dishes were incubated for twenty-four hours at 37°C. Transparent areas formed around colonies after incubation with positive lipase positive colonies were counted. This process was performed in triplicate.³³

2.4 Determination of salt concentrations, temperatures and pH values for each isolate

Complex Media containing different salt concentrations (0.5%, 3%, 5%, 7.5%, 10%, 12.5% and 15%) and Complex Media without salt were used to examine salt requirement and salt tolerance of isolates. Complex Media adjusted at different pH values (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12) to determine the optimum pH value were used to examine the pH requirement and pH tolerance of slightly halophilic bacterial isolates. To determine the optimum temperature, Petri dishes were incubated at varying temperatures (55, 45, 37, 28, 20, 10 and 4°C).⁵

2.5 Enzymatic activity tests of isolates

Amylase, lipase, xylanase, protease, DNase, pullulanase, cellulase, urease and β -galactosidase enzyme activities of the isolates were investigated. Amylase activity was investigated in Starch Medium (25g starch, 5g agar, 1000ml SW3). Gram's iodine solution was poured to cover the pure bacterial colonies growing on the petri dish. The observation of a transparent region around the colonies was considered amylase activity.^{34,35} Xylanase activity was tested on Xylane Medium (1g AZCL-xylan, 10g agar, 1000ml SW3). Transparent areas formed around the colonies growing on the petri dish were accepted as positive xylanase activity.³³ Protease and lipase activities were tested as 'Detection of Total Number of Proteolytic and Lipolytic Slightly Halophilic Bacteria'.³⁴ 1N HCl was poured on the colonies growing on DNase Medium (40g DNase agar, 5g agar, 1000ml SW3) and it was tested whether the isolates could cleave DNA. The formation of a clear area around the colonies was considered DNase activity.³³ Pullulanase activity was tested on Pullulan Medium (10g AZCL-pullulano, 20g agar, 1000ml SW3). Transparent regions formed around the colonies were considered as positive pullulanase activities.³³ Cellulase activity was tested on Cellulose Medium (2g carboxymethyl cellulose, 1g yeast extract, 1000ml SW3). After staining for 30 minutes by pouring 0.1% Congo Red solution on the bacterial colonies grown in Cellulose Medium, 1M NaCl solution was poured to remove excess dye. Bacterial colonies with a clear zone around them were considered to have positive cellulase activity. Urease activity was tested on Urease Medium (15g urea, 1000ml SW3). The pink colour of the medium was evaluated as urease activity. β -galactosidase activity of slightly halophilic bacterial strains was investigated. Colonies of slightly halophilic bacteria grown in Complex Media containing 3% salt were picked with a loop and inoculating in 0.2ml of

sterile 3% FTS solution containing ONPG disc (Oxoid), and the tubes were incubated for twenty-four hours in incubator at 3°C. The change of the liquid in the tube to yellow colour was considered as a positive result.^{33,34}

2.6 Biochemical tests of isolates

Gram staining reactions of isolates were tested by the acetic-acid fixation method.³⁶ Catalase activity was tested by dropping 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution onto pure colonies grown on Complex Media. The formation of gas bubbles around the colonies was considered as positive catalase activity.³³ The oxidase activity was tested by taking a sterile loop from pure bacterial colonies grown on Complex Agar Medium and applying it on filter paper on which para-aminodimethylaniline-monohydrochloride reagent was poured. The occurrence of a blue-violet colour within 5-10 seconds was considered a positive result.^{34,35} Citrate activity was tested on Citrate Medium (25g citrate agar, 1000ml SW3) prepared as slant agar. A blue colour of the medium is considered a positive result.³³ The ability of the isolates to produce acids using different carbohydrates was investigated. Different carbohydrates were sterilised in a membrane filter (D-xylose, xylitol, D-mannose, D-ribose, sucrose) and put into tubes at 1%. After the medium (0.5% yeast extract, 0.001% phenol red) was thoroughly mixed, the isolates were seeded and incubated for twenty four hours in incubator at 37°C. A change in the colour of the medium to yellow was accepted as a positive result.^{33,34} The capability of isolates to degrade amino acids in the skin structure was tested by inoculating isolates into tubes containing amino acid decarboxylase medium (0.0005% cresol red, 0.05% dextrose, 3% NaCl solution, 0.5% peptone, 0.001% bromocresol purple, 0.5% beef extract, 0.0005% pyridoxal) and 1% amino acid (L-glycine, L-threonine, L-cysteine, L-arginine, L-alanine) solutions.³³ If the amino acids in the medium undergo fermentation, the colour turns purple due to the alkaline amine compounds that emerge as the final product.

2.7 Molecular identification

Chromosomal DNA was isolated and then purified with the help of a QIAamp-DNA Mini Kit (QIAGEN). This process was carried out taking into account the instructions indicated in the Kit procedure. DNA isolation was visualised and checked by agarose gel electrophoresis. The 16S rRNA gene regions of the isolates were PCR amplified using universal primers 16F27; [5'-AGAGT TTGAT CMTGGCTCAG-3'] and 16R1488; [5'-CGGT TACCTTGTTA GGACTTCACC-3'].³⁷ PCR products were analysed by Arti Biotechnology Laboratory, Turkey for base sequence analysis of the 16S rRNA gene. The similarity rates of the 16S rRNA sequences obtained were determined by the ChromasPro Program, EZTAXON and BLAST search programs. 16S rRNA sequence data of the isolates SaShS1a, SaShS1b, SaShS2a, SaShS2b, SaShS3a, SaShS3b, SaShS4a, SaShS4b, SaShS5a, SaShS5b, SaShS6a, SaShS6b, SaShS7a, SaShS8a, SaShS8b, SaShS9a, SaShS10a, SaShS10b reported

in this article have been deposited in GenBank nucleotide sequence database under the respective accession numbers: OR133543, OR133544, OR133545, OR133546, OR133547, OR133548, OR133549, OR133550, OR133551, OR133552, OR133553, OR133554, OR133555, OR133556, OR133557, OR133558, OR133559, OR133560.

2.8 Investigation of bacteriocin production capabilities of slightly halophilic bacteria

Slightly halophilic bacterial isolates were grown in 20ml of Liquid Complex Medium containing 3% salt at 37°C for 48 hours. To obtain a cell-free supernatant (CFS) from the prepared bacterial solution, it was centrifuged at 8000g for ten minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was filtered with the help of 0.45µm membrane filters and sterile pure bacteriocin was thus obtained.³² Then, the isolates were incubated in 20ml of 3% Salt Liquid Complex Media at 37°C for 48 hours, and the density of each of the isolates was adjusted to McFarland 0.5 (10⁸CFU/ml) with a densitometer. 3µl of cell-free bacteriocin-containing supernatant (CFS) was put into the petri dishes inoculated with prepared bacterial suspension. At the end of 48 hours, the transparent zones formed around the colonies were determined. According to the results, bacteriocin producing isolates, bacteriocin sensitive isolates and bacteriocin resistant isolates were determined.

2.9 Effects of different environmental conditions on bacteriocin activity

In our study, the effects of different temperatures, pH, salt concentrations and enzymes on bacteriocin activity were investigated. CFS (cell-free supernatants) from each bacterial solution were treated at different temperatures (4, 19, 24, 37, 50, 60, 70°C) for 15 minutes to examine the effects of temperature on bacteriocin activity.³² The bacteriocin was treated at different pH values (from 4 to 10) for 3 hours and effect of pH on bacteriocin activity was determined.^{32,38} Bacteriocin was treated with different salt concentration values (3%, 5%, 10%, 20%). The effect of salt on bacteriocin activity was determined.^{32,38} In order to examine the effects of different enzymes on bacteriocin activity, proteinase K (10mM phosphate buffer) and lipase (Tris HCl 0.05M and CaCl₂ 0.01M) enzymes were prepared in the specified buffer solutions, filtered (10mg/mL) and sterilised.^{32,38} Enzymes were treated with bacteriocin for 2 hours after adjusting the final concentration to 1mg/ml. 3µl of these prepared supernatants were taken with the help of a micropipette and added to the other slightly halophilic bacterial isolates planted on Complex Medium containing 3% salt. Petri dishes were incubated for twenty-four hours in incubator at 37°C. The inhibition zones formed were examined and the most suitable environmental conditions for bacteriocin activity were determined. Tris-HCl buffer (0.05M) and phosphate buffer (10mM) were used as negative control of lipase and proteinase K enzymes, respectively.

2.10 Determination of susceptibility of isolated slightly halophilic bacteria to antimicrobial agent by disk diffusion method

The effectiveness of an active antimicrobial agent containing sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate as used in the leather industry, on our isolated slightly halophilic bacteria was tested at eighteen different concentrations (4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.2, 15.6, 7.8, 3.9, 1.96, 0.98, 0.49, 0.24, 0.12, 0.06 and 0.03µg/ml).²⁷ Pure colonies of isolates grown on Complex Agar Media and the tubes were incubated for twenty-four hours in an incubator at 37°C. After incubation, bacterial suspensions of slightly halophilic bacteria were prepared according to the 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard (108kob/ml). The Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was used in our study. Ten µl of solutions of different concentrations of the antimicrobial agent were taken and absorbed into sterile discs. Then, each bacterial isolate was spread homogeneously on the Complex Media. The discs containing different concentrations of the test antimicrobial were placed on Complex Media and petri dishes were incubated for twenty-four hours in incubator at 37°C. The zones around the discs were measured in mm and the concentrations at which the antimicrobial was effective were determined.^{27,35}

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, the total number of slightly halophilic bacteria, total number of proteolytic slightly halophilic bacteria and total number of lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria from the sheepskin samples were determined as $1 \times 10^4 - 4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g, $2 \times 10^3 - 4 \times 10^4$ CFU/g and $1 \times 10^2 - 3 \times 10^4$ CFU/g, respectively (Table I). These numbers of slightly halophilic bacteria were relatively high. The reason for the development of slightly halophilic bacteria on sheepskin may be due to the salt curing process applied with untreated dry salt for long-term preservation in the warehouses. If the skins are not salted homogeneously, and the environmental conditions (humidity, temperature, errors in the stacking process of the skins, incorrect storage conditions) are suitable for bacterial growth, an excellent environment for the growth of halophilic bacteria may be provided.^{22,39} Our results show similarities with the previous studies evaluating the number of moderately halophilic or extremely halophilic bacteria in skin/hide samples. In a study examining 35 salt-cured hide samples imported from Russia and France, it was reported that the hide samples contained 86% moderately halophilic bacteria, 37% slightly halophilic bacteria, 29% halotolerant bacteria, and 91% extremely halophilic archaea.¹⁴ In another study, the number of moderately halophilic bacteria, proteolytic, and lipolytic moderately halophilic bacteria from five salted skin samples were determined as 10^2-10^7 CFU/g, 10^1-10^5 CFU/g and 10^5-10^6 CFU/g, respectively.⁵ Akpolat *et al.* (2015) reported the number of moderately halophilic bacteria isolated from salted sheepskins with yellow

and red colourations imported from Spain as 10^9-10^8 CFU/g.¹⁰ Differences in the total number of bacteria between studies may vary according to the random use of salt by the tanners in the warehouses, the use of untreated salts with the potential to contain halophilic bacteria, the environmental conditions of the warehouses or tanneries (temperature, humidity *etc.*), the regions where the samples were taken from the stacked raw hides, or the season the sample was taken *etc.*^{2,40} Also, it is noteworthy that most of our isolates have proteolytic and lipolytic activities and their numbers are not to be underestimated. As known, proteolytic and lipolytic archaea are responsible from bad odour, red heat, hair loss, disruption of collagen fibres *etc.* that cause loss of quality for the finished

TABLE I
The total number of slightly halophilic bacteria, proteolytic slightly halophilic bacteria and lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria in sheepskin samples (CFU/g)

Sample code	Total number of slightly halophilic bacteria	Total number of proteolytic slightly halophilic bacteria	Total number of lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria
SaShS1	2×10^4	1×10^4	8×10^3
SaShS2	2×10^4	1×10^4	1×10^3
SaShS3	4×10^5	1×10^4	1×10^2
SaShS4	1×10^4	6×10^3	4×10^3
SaShS5	1×10^4	2×10^3	1×10^3
SaShS6	2×10^4	2×10^4	2×10^4
SaShS7	3×10^4	3×10^3	1×10^3
SaShS8	4×10^4	1×10^4	1×10^4
SaShS9	1×10^4	4×10^3	2×10^3
SaShS10	1×10^5	4×10^4	3×10^4

*SaShS: Salted sheepskin sample

product.^{2,4,5,41} In this respect, it suggests that our isolates may have similar effects.

In our study, eighteen slightly halophilic bacterial strains were isolated from sheepskin samples and they were identified by both traditional microbiological and molecular techniques (Tables II-III-IV). The salt tolerance of these isolates was investigated. None of the isolates showed growth at 0% and 15% salt concentrations (Table II). The isolates were considered as halophiles because they did not grow on salt-free media.⁴² It was determined that the isolates encoded with SaShS1a, SaShS1b, SaShS2b, SaShS3a, SaShS3b, SaShS4b, SaShS5b, SaShS10a, and SaShS10b were found to be able to grow in the range of 0.5%-10% salt concentration, whereas SaShS5a, SaShS8b, SaShS9a could grow in the salt concentration of 0.5%-7.5%, SaShS2a, SaShS4a, SaShS6a, SaShS6b, SaShS7a, SaShS8a were grown in the salt concentration of 0.5-12.5% salt concentrations (Table II). The optimum salt concentration where the isolates grew was determined as 3-5% and in this context, these isolates were evaluated as slightly halophiles. None of the isolates

TABLE II
Salt concentration, pH and temperature range results in which slightly halophilic bacteria isolates can grow

Isolate code	Salt tolerance (%)															pH range										Temperature range (°C)				
	0	0.5	3	5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	4	10	20	28	37	45	55						
SaShS1a	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS1b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS2a	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS2b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS3a	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS3b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS4a	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS4b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS5a	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS5b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS6a	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS6b	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS7a	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS8a	-	+	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS8b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS9a	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS10a	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						
SaShS10b	-	+	++	++	++	+	-	-	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++	++	-						

* (++) excellent growth, (+) weak growth, (-) no growth.

were able to grow at pH5 and 12. The SaShS9a isolate grew only at pH7-8 (Table II). The optimum pH values for the growth of isolates are found to be pH7 and 8. None of the isolates grew at 4 and 55°C (Table II). It was observed that our isolates grow optimally at the temperatures of 37 and 45°C. In a previous research, it has been reported that slightly halophilic bacteria can tolerate salt concentrations of 2-10%, pH5-10 and temperatures up to 55°C.^{18,20,21}

Slightly halophilic bacterial strains isolated from salted sheepskin samples were molecularly identified. According to the results of 16S rRNA sequence analysis, it was determined that the bacterial isolates belonged to the *Bacillus* genus (Table III). Eighteen slightly halophilic bacteria isolated from salted sheepskin samples were defined as *Bacillus haynesii* (SaShS1a, SaShS2b, SaShS3a, SaShS3b, SaShS4b, SaShS5b, SaShS10a, SaShS10b), *Bacillus rugosus* (SaShS1b), *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a), *Bacillus mojavenis* (SaShS5a), *Bacillus safensis* (SaShS2a, SaShS4a, SaShS8a), *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (SaShS6b), *Bacillus atrophaeus* (SaShS6a), *Bacillus kochii* (SaShS9a), *Bacillus pumilus* (SaShS8b). The codes, similarity ratios (%), base lengths (bp) and phylogenetic similarity of the isolates are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Isolate codes, base length (bp), similarity rate (%), phylogenetically similar species and accession numbers of slightly halophilic bacteria isolates

Isolate code	Base length (bp)	Similarity rate (%)	Closest relative	GenBank accession number
SaShS1a	1508	99.53	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133543
SaShS1b	1548	99.25	<i>B. rugosus</i>	OR133544
SaShS2a	1474	99.63	<i>B. safensis</i>	OR133545
SaShS2b	1508	99.54	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133546
SaShS3a	1508	99.32	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133547
SaShS3b	1508	99.18	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133548
SaShS4a	1474	99.90	<i>B. safensis</i>	OR133549
SaShS4b	1508	99.50	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133550
SaShS5a	1407	99.69	<i>B. mojavenis</i>	OR133551
SaShS5b	1508	99.17	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133552
SaShS6a	1475	99.56	<i>B. atrophaeus</i>	OR133553
SaShS6b	1468	99.47	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	OR133554
SaShS7a	1466	99.46	<i>B. aerius</i>	OR133555
SaShS8a	1474	99.90	<i>B. safensis</i>	OR133556
SaShS8b	1434	99.48	<i>B. pumilus</i>	OR133557
SaShS9a	1511	99.37	<i>B. kochii</i>	OR133558
SaShS10a	1508	99.29	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133559
SaShS10b	1508	99.74	<i>B. haynesii</i>	OR133560

When the frequency of presence of isolates in salted sheepskin samples was examined, the most common bacterial strains in skin samples were *Bacillus haynesii* (in 6 skin samples) and *Bacillus safensis* (in 3 skin

samples) (Table IV). *Bacillus atrophaeus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Bacillus rugosus*, *Bacillus aerius*, *Bacillus kochii* and *Bacillus mojavenis* each of which were detected in 1 skin sample (Table IV). In previous work, there are studies in which *Bacillus* were isolated from skin/hides samples. In such a study, 21 isolates of *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus sphaericus*, *Micrococcus roseus*, *Kurthia variabilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* were isolated from 10 freshly cut fresh cattle skins collected from slaughterhouses in Istanbul. All *Bacillus* species and two *Staphylococcus aureus* strains were found to be able to digest gelatin.⁴³ In a study, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus circulans*, *Bacillus pantothenicus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Achromobacter liquefaciens*, *Brevibacterium insectiphilum*, *Alcaligenes marshalli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus roseus* strains were isolated from three fresh goatskins obtained from India.⁴⁴ In another study, 668 bacteria were isolated from salted skin samples. As a result of the study, it was reported that the most common bacterial genera in skin samples were *Bacillus*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Enterococcus* and *Staphylococcus*.⁴⁵ In a study, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus anthrocoides* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacterial strains were isolated from samples taken from areas with bad odour on the skin. These bacterial strains have also been reported to cause holes in the skin.⁴⁶ The presence of species belonging to the genus *Bacillus*, which cause deterioration in the structure of skins/hides in both fresh raw skin samples and salted sheepskin samples that have been preserved with salt and stored indicates insufficient salting process. In addition, salt which are used for the protection of the skins/hides can also be a potential source of contamination. In a supporting study, researchers isolated 83 halotolerant bacteria from salt samples taken from 14 different leather factories in Tuzla and Çorlu (Turkey), and belonged to the genus *Bacillus*.⁴⁷ In addition, it has been reported that bacteria species belonging to the genus *Bacillus* cause rancidity in raw hides, salted leathers and in the tanning stage of leather.⁴⁸

All of the slightly halophilic bacteria strains isolated from salted sheepskin samples were Gram-positive and rod-shaped. 44% of the isolates showed citrate activity. 50%, 83%, 77% and %88 isolates used D-xylose, D-mannose, D-ribose and sucrose as carbon sources, respectively. None of the isolates could use xylitol (Table V). In previous studies, the amino acids found in the skin's structure were determined as proline, alanine, cysteine, glutamic acid, hydroxyproline, glycine, arginine, serine, lysine, leucine, valine, isoleucine, histidine and trosine.¹ It was determined that 27%, 27%, 22% and 22% of the isolates could use L-cysteine, L-glycine, L-alanine and L-threonine amino acids, respectively. None of the isolates used the amino acid L-arginine (Table V). 100%, 83%, 61%, 88%, 11% and 44% isolates showed protease, DNase, lipase, cellulase, pullulanase

TABLE IV
Frequency of slightly halophilic bacteria isolates in salted sheepskins

Isolates	Salted sheepskin samples										Total number
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	3
<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Bacillus haynesii</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	6
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	1
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Bacillus rugosus</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Bacillus aerius</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	1
<i>Bacillus kochii</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	1
<i>Bacillus mojavensis</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	1

*The (+) value represents the presence of bacteria, the (-) value represents the absence of bacteria.

and xylanase activity, respectively. None of the isolates showed amylase, urease and β -galactosidase activity (Table V). Enzymes produced by halophilic bacteria are biotechnologically important because of their stability at high temperatures, their low cost, and their high catalytic activity in high salt conditions.⁴⁹ It was reported that 8 salted skin samples from Iraq, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, and Armenia were contaminated with halophilic archaea and the isolates showed 57% protease, 35% esterase, 11% amylase and 18% lipase activity.⁵⁰ In a study conducted in Spain, it was reported that halophilic bacteria isolated from different hypersaline environments showed amylase, lipase, protease and DNase activities.⁵¹ In a study of 131 salt-cured bovine leather samples imported from the USA, salted leather samples were reported to be contaminated by halophilic archaea (332 strains). In the continuation of this study, they stated that 94% of halophilic archaea isolated from skin samples showed proteolytic activity.² These studies showed parallelism with our study and it is understood that halophilic micro-organisms have high hydrolytic activity. The high extracellular enzyme activities cause deterioration in the skin, digesting the protein and fat that are found in the structure of the skin at high rates. Especially since the sheepskin samples we used in our study have a high fat content compared to other cattle hides, they can be digested by lipolytic slightly halophilic bacteria and their structure can be damaged. However, this metabolic activity is promising for use in biotechnological studies at high salt concentrations. In future studies, whether the enzymes produced by slightly halophilic bacteria strains could be used in the leather industry can be determined by evaluating various parameters.

In our study, 9 isolates belonging to the genus *Bacillus* were investigated to determine their ability to produce bacteriocins active against each other. *Bacillus safensis* (SaShS2a), *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a), *Bacillus haynesii* (SaShS1a) and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (SaShS6b) showed antagonistic effects on respectively 1, 5, 3 and 1 isolates (Table VI).

There are studies investigating the antimicrobial activities of isolates of the genus *Bacillus*. For example, *Bacillus pumilus* SF214 bacterial strain isolated from sea water has been reported to produce a bacteriocin-like antimicrobial substance named Pumilacidin against pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria monocytogenes*.⁵² In addition, it has been stated in previous studies that bacteria belonging to the *Bacillus* genus produce active compounds such as bacteriocins, antibiotics, antimicrobial peptides and lipopeptides. In particular, studies have been carried out on the antibiotic production of *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis*. The reasons why *Bacillus* species are attractive as biological control agents have been reported as their abundance in many extreme habitats, production of biologically active metabolites, and ability to form resistant spores.⁵³ In our study, bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) showed antibacterial effect on *Bacillus pumilus* (SaShS8b), *Bacillus safensis* (SaShS2a), *Bacillus atrophaeus* (SaShS6a), *Bacillus haynesii* (SaShS1a) and *Bacillus rugosus* (SaShS1b) isolates (Table VI). In previous studies, it has been reported that the content of the medium, culture conditions such as pH and temperature affect bacteriocin production in *Bacillus* species.⁵⁴ Therefore, more detailed studies have been carried out for bacteriocin characterisation. *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) showed higher antibacterial activity than other isolates. For this reason, bacteriocin studies were continued with this isolate. Optimum environmental conditions were investigated for bacteriocin activity (Table VII).

Bacteriocin activity by *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) did not lose its antimicrobial activity after 15 minutes of heat treatment at 4, 19, 24, 37, 50°C, but completely lost its activity after 15 minutes of heat treatment at 60 and 70°C (Table VII). In a study, it was stated that bacteriocin produced by the halotolerant *Brevibacterium linens* isolated from salty cheeses did not lose activity at 25 and 30°C.⁵⁵ The thermostable structure of bacteriocins is important for their use as bioprotective in biotechnological applications.³⁰ It was

TABLE V
Biochemical characteristics and enzymatic activity results of isolates

Characteristics	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. rugosus</i>	<i>B. safensis</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. safensis</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. mojavensis</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. atrophaeus</i>	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>B. aerius</i>	<i>B. safensis</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. kochii</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. haynesii</i>	No. of positive isolates	Perc. of positive isolates
	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods		
Cell morphology	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods	rods		
Gram staining	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
Oxidase	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	18	100
Catalase	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	18	100
Citrate utilisation	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	8	44
Acid production from different sugar sources																				
D-xylose	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	9	50
Xylitol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
D-mannose	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	15	83
D-ribose	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	14	77
Sucrose	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	16	88
Amino acid decarboxylase test																				
L-cysteine	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	5	27
L-glycine	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	5	27
L-alanine	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	4	22
L-threonine	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	4	22
L-arginine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0	0
Enzymatic activity tests																				
Protease	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	18	100
DNase	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	15	83
Urease	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
Lipase	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	11	61
Cellulase	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	16	88
Pullulanase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	11
Xylanase	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	8	44
Amylase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0
β -galactosidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0

determined that bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) isolate showed antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus rugosus* (SaShS1b) (pH4-9), *Bacillus atrophaeus* (SaShS6a) and *Bacillus pumilus* (SaShS8b) (pH4-10) isolates at wide pH ranges (Table VII). It has been reported that bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus subtilis* HD15 strain isolated from traditional fermented soybean paste remains stable in wide pH (2-10) ranges.⁵⁶ Bacteriocin activity was studied at salt concentrations of 3%, 5%, 10%, and 20%. Inhibition was observed in all isolates at 3% salt concentration. Zones of inhibition were observed at high salt concentrations against *Bacillus safensis* (SaShS2a)

and *Bacillus atrophaeus* (SaShS6a) isolates (Table VII). The activity of bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) isolate was completely destroyed after treatment with proteinase K enzyme. However, it was determined that it did not lose its activity after being treated with the lipase enzyme and formed an inhibition zone (Table VII).

In another study, it was reported that a bacteriocin produced by *Bacillus subtilis* H27 bacterial strain lost its activity after treatment with proteinase K and protease enzymes, but remained active after treatment with enzymes such as trypsin and pepsin.³⁸ Additionally, in a study, it was stated that bacteriocin

TABLE VI
Bacteriocin production of slightly halophilic bacterial isolates against each other

Isolate code	Isolates	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. rugosus</i>	<i>B. safensis</i>	<i>B. mojavensis</i>	<i>B. atrophaeus</i>	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>B. aerius</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. kochii</i>
SaShS1a	<i>Bacillus haynesii</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+
SaShS1b	<i>Bacillus rugosus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SaShS2a	<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
SaShS5a	<i>Bacillus mojavensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SaShS6a	<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SaShS6b	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
SaShS7a	<i>Bacillus aerius</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-
SaShS8b	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SaShS9a	<i>Bacillus kochii</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*(+) : There is an inhibition zone, (-) : There is no inhibition zone.

obtained from *Bacillus subtilis* HD15 bacterial strain completely lost its activity when treated with proteinase K, protease and pronase E.⁵⁶ These results show that bacteriocins have a protein structure. As a result, the bacteriocin we obtained showed activity in all isolates at 4, 19, 24 and 37°C temperature values, pH4, 3% salt concentration and presence of lipase enzyme (Table VII). In our study, the strain affected by the bacteriocin produced by the highest number of isolates was *Bacillus atrophaeus* (SaShS6a), and it was affected by the bacteriocin produced by 3 isolates (*Bacillus safensis*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Bacillus aerius*). *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (SaShS6b) bacterial strain was not affected by the bacteriocin produced by other isolates. Considering the results of our study, bacteriocins can be considered as an alternative to overcome the problem of antimicrobial resistance caused by the unconscious use of antimicrobial agents utilised in leather manufacturing processes.

The sensitivity of slightly halophilic bacteria isolates to the active ingredient sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate (40%) used in the leather industry was investigated. An inhibition zone over 25mm against tested antimicrobial agent was observed in all bacterial isolates at a concentration of 4000µg/ml. At a concentration of 4000µg/mL, inhibition zones were recorded as 25mm for *Bacillus haynesii*, *Bacillus rugosus* and *Bacillus atrophaeus*, 32mm for *Bacillus safensis*, 27mm for *Bacillus mojavensis* and *Bacillus aerius*, 30mm for *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and *Bacillus kochii*, 2mm for *Bacillus pumilus* (Table VIII). As the concentration of tested antimicrobial agent

decreased, the diameter of inhibition zones of the isolates also decreased (Table VIII).

Our tested isolates were found to be sensitive to the sodium diethyldithiocarbamate active ingredient (40%). The antimicrobial substance showed effect against all bacterial isolates at concentrations of 4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 250, 125µg/mL (Table VIII). The concentration value of 62.5µg/mL was found to affect other isolates except *Bacillus rugosus*. MIC values of the isolates were determined as 62.5µg/mL (*Bacillus rugosus*), 31.2µg/mL (*Bacillus haynesii*, *Bacillus safensis*, *Bacillus mojavensis*) 15.6µg/mL (*Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Bacillus aerius*, *Bacillus kochii*) 7.8µg/mL (*Bacillus pumilus*) and 3.9µg/mL (*Bacillus atrophaeus*).

When fresh raw skins/hides are salted with untreated dry salt, it affects the quality of the finished leather and causes economic losses because it may contain various detrimental halophilic bacteria and halophilic archaea. For this reason, some chemicals such as various disinfectants, chlorides, antiseptics, biocides, potassium chloride, boric acid, naphthalene and carbamic acid salts are used, either alone or along with salt.^{4,35,57} In addition, physical methods such as cooling, vacuum pressing, use of electric current or electron beams have also been tried in previous studies.^{39,58-60} Various lichen extracts, plant extracts and antibiotics have also been tested for their antimicrobial effects in the leather industry.⁶¹⁻⁶⁴ Small amounts and indiscriminate use of antimicrobial agents fail to control bacterial numbers, while excessive use causes bacteria to develop resistance to

TABLE VII Determining optimum environmental conditions for bacteriocin activity					
	<i>Bacillus haynesii</i>	<i>Bacillus rugosus</i>	<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>
Isolate Code	SaShS1a	SaShS1b	SaShS2a	SaShS6a	SaShS8b
Parameters					
Enzyme production	Protease and lipase	Protease and lipase	Protease	Protease	Protease and lipase
Temperature values (°C)					
4	+	+	+	+	+
19	+	+	+	+	+
24	+	+	+	+	+
37	+	+	+	+	+
50	-	+	+	+	+
60	-	-	-	-	-
70	-	-	-	-	-
pH					
4	+	+	+	+	+
5	-	+	+	+	+
6	-	+	+	+	+
7	-	+	-	+	+
8	-	+	-	+	+
9	-	+	-	+	+
10	-	+	+		
Salt concentration (%) values					
3	+	+	+	+	+
5	-	+	+	+	+
10	-	+	+	-	-
20	-	+	-	+	-
Enzyme					
Proteinase K	-	-	-	-	-
Lipase	+	+	+	+	+
*(+) : There is an inhibition zone, (-) : There is no inhibition zone.					

antimicrobial agents. The selection of antimicrobial agents and the determination of their appropriate concentrations are important in terms of preventing damage to the skin caused by bacteria.

4 CONCLUSIONS

One of the major problems encountered in the leather industry is bacterial damage that leads to serious quality losses in the finished product. To the best of our knowledge, there is no study evaluating the presence of slightly halophilic bacteria in sheepskins and their identification via traditional microbiological and molecular techniques. In the present study, our slightly halophilic bacterial isolates were rod-shaped, Gram-positive, and have positive oxidase and catalase activities. It was determined that the isolates had high hydrolytic activity (protease, DNase, xylanase lipase, pullulanase and cellulase). According to the molecular identification analyses, all isolates were determined to

be in the genus *Bacillus*. In addition, it has been determined that our isolates have an antagonistic effect by producing bacteriocins against each other. The impact of different temperatures, salt concentrations, different enzymes and pH values on the bacteriocin activity produced by *Bacillus aerius* (SaShS7a) were investigated. It has been determined that bacteriocin is in a thermostable structure and does not lose its activity at high pH and salt values. It completely lost its activity with the bacteriocin proteinase K enzyme, but retained its activity after treatment with the lipase enzyme. It has been predicted that this bacteriocin can be used to control slightly halophilic bacteria in the leather industry.

The susceptibility of the isolates to the antimicrobial agent containing sodium diethyldithiocarbamate which is used in the leather industry was investigated by the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. It was determined that the slightly halophilic bacteria that we isolated were sensitive to this chemical at the concentrations of 4000,

TABLE VIII
Antimicrobial effect of tested antimicrobial agent against isolates of slightly halophilic bacteria

	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	<i>B. haynesii</i>	<i>B. rugosus</i>	<i>B. safensis</i>	<i>B. mojavensis</i>	<i>B. atrophaeus</i>	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>B. aerius</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. kochii</i>
1	4000	25	25	32	27	25	30	27	28	30
2	2000	19	20	31	25	18	22	23	24	25
3	1000	18	19	30	15	14	20	21	20	20
4	500	15	17	25	12	13	15	18	17	19
5	250	14	15	17	11	10	15	17	15	16
6	125	14	13	10	9	10	14	16	13	15
7	62.5	11	-	9	7	9	10	12	12	12
8	31.2	-	-	-	-	9	10	9	12	10
9	15.6	-	-	-	-	8	-	-	10	-
10	7.8	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	-
11	3.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	1.96	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	0.98	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	0.49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	0.12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*(+): There is no inhibition zone.

2000, 1000, 500, 250 and 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. In general, these results show that the salts used to protect the skins/hides contain metabolically active slightly halophilic bacteria. These have the potential to digest the components found in the structure of the skin, especially with the hydrolytic enzymes produced by *Bacillus* bacteria. Considering this situation, this approach can be an alternative to the salting method using natural antimicrobial substances such as bacteriocin, which can be used to prevent skin/hides contamination. In addition, the fact that bacterial strains of the *Bacillus* genus protect themselves with the endospore structure makes it difficult to fight against these bacteria. To prevent this situation, the stacking areas of the skins/hides should be changed at regular intervals to activate the spore structure and bactericides should be applied at appropriate concentrations.

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